

ISic0414

I.Sicily inscription 0414

Language

Latin

Type

(?)

Material

marble

Object

fragment

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 6794

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]LI[---]
2. [---]LATYR[---]
3. [---]RI Ioves [---]
4. [---]IOR Sicul[---]
5. [---]PAMPINE[---]
6. [---]Sirac[---]
6. [---]PP[---]

Apparatus

CIL transcript shows that the last two letters are either two 'l's or two 'i's or one of both; perhaps 'Pampinell[a-]' or 'pampinei l/i[---]'.

CIL, citing Benndorf: either 'pp' or 'sp'.

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491645

EDCS 21900477

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7134 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650767>)

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